

ACOUSTIC EMISSION MONITORING OF TENSILE TESTING OF LOW VELOCITY IMPACT-DAMAGED CFRP LAMINATES

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ABSTRACT

CFRP coupons damaged by low velocity impact were tested under static tensile loading and the progress of damage was monitored by acoustic emission. The degree of impact damage has been correlated with the acoustic emission activity during monotonic or loading/unloading tensile testing. Special attention was paid to determine optimal parameters of acoustic emission signals to characterize the microscopic fracture process of the composite laminates. RMS voltage of acoustic emission signals during the early stage of tensile loading was found to be an effective parameter to quantify the degree of impact damage. A newly defined parameter, integrity ratio, based on the rms voltage is also proposed.

INTRODUCTION

Impact damage can be a serious problem in the structures made of brittle materials such as composite laminates. Polymer matrix composite laminates whose applications to aerospace structures are steadily increasing are likely to be damaged by low velocity impact of various moving objects such as tools, runway stones, ice balls, and even birds. For the damage assessment and residual strength determination, a variety of NDE techniques have been employed, either alone or in combination, such as ultrasonic C-scan, X-radiography, acousto-ultrasonics and acoustic emission.

Acoustic emission (AE) has been successfully applied to detect and locate the damaged area of impact-damaged composites during the subsequent quasi-static or low-cycle fatigue loading[1-3]. They found that the severer the damage is, the more emission and the lower the stress level at which it initiates[1,2]. Although the impact damage is generally non-visual and was unable to be located during quasi-static loading, it could be easily detected and located under tension-tension cyclic loading even within a few cycle[1]. It was also found that long duration events could be used to differentiate between stable and unstable behavior and to predict residual strength when unstable behavior occurred. The normalized cumulative event rate moment and the average event rates

are also proposed to be a useful feature for the discrimination[3]. AE event duration distributions during the initial load hold are, however, reported as independent of the degree of damage.

In this study, we have tried to find one or more optimal AE parameters for the damage assessment and the residual strength prediction of low velocity impact-damaged CFRP composite laminates.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials and Specimens

Specimens were from fully cured composite panels made by autoclave molding with high strength carbon/epoxy prepreg(RS1222, Toho Rayon Co.) which has elongation of 1.16%. Type-A specimens have stacking sequence of $[\pm 45/0/90]_S$ and type-B specimens of $[\pm 45]_{2S}$ so that their tensile strength are 803MPa and 224MPa, respectively. The configuration and dimension of specimen with the position marked at which the impact damage was introduced are shown in Fig. 1. The degree of impact damage was adjusted by changing the impact velocity from 0.71 to 2.17 m/sec to be rated as 10%, 30%, and 50% with reference to the total absorbed energy at fracture as 100%.

Figure 1 Configuration and dimension of impact-damaged CFRP specimens

Tensile Tests

An electro-mechanical type Instron(Model 8162) was used under stroke control for monotonic loading and under load control for loading-unloading testing. The crosshead speed of 0.5mm/min was the same for all specimens under stroke control whereas the loading rates were 1.28kN/min and 0.27kN/min for type-A and type-B, respectively. The unloading points to obtain the felicity ratio(FR) were 40%, 60%, 70% and 80% of the ultimate strength for type-A specimens and 30%, 50%, 70% and 90% of that for type-B specimens.

AE Data Acquisition

A schematic diagram of the data acquisition system is shown in Fig.2. An AE sensor with wide band response(WD/PAC) and a strain gage were attached at each side to the closest position to damaged area. Detected signals were amplified by 60dB with 125kHz to 1MHz bandpass filtering then fed into signal processors including a transient recorder as described elsewhere. The intensity of AE activity was recorded by a true RMS voltmeter(HP3400A) together with load and strain on a chart recorder and on a computer. Threshold was set at $20\mu V$ at the sensor. A microcomputer-based AE instrumentation(AET5500) was employed to collect the events and to extract the AE parameters. A number of digital waveforms were also recorded using a storage oscilloscope(LeCroy 9340).

Figure 2 A schematic diagram of the data acquisition system

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

AE RMS Voltage

RMS voltage of AE signals is a typical parameter recorded during most of AE experiments for its simplicity and real time display. AE intensity in rms voltage during the monotonic loading was plotted together with load for damaged specimens of both type-A and type-B as shown in Fig. 3. With the increasing degree of impact damage, the activity during the initial stage prior to the major ply failure was increased and the time for initiating the activity was also considerably shortened. The periods are taken as approximately up to 400sec for type-A specimens and up to 300sec for type-B specimens, respectively. After the period, regardless of the type of specimens, the baselines of the rms voltage curve are starting to float and to show an upward slope. The activity during this period has been known as the friction generated acoustic emission [1]. The amount of the friction generated AE or the AE during the initial stage of loading showed a close relationship with the degree of impact damage. RMS voltage level was then taken as the indication of the onset of the friction generated AE activity and a newly defined parameter has been calculated in terms of the load level. The parameter will be discussed in more detail later in this section.

Figure 3 AE intensity and load vs. time during monotonic tensile loading

AE Event Duration

Two representative AE events data with time (or displacement) from each type of specimens are shown in Fig. 4. Fig. 4(a) from type-A specimen with 10% damage indicates much less AE events than Fig. 4(b) from type-B specimen with 50% damage. Analysis with AE waveform parameters such as distributions of energy or peak amplitude by events was also carried out. The results from the distributions itself, however, were not very useful to differentiate between the degree of damage.

When peak amplitude is plotted against event duration, AE signals from different state of materials or structures often can be differentiated. In Fig. 5, AE events during the initial period indicated as "analysis window" in Fig. 4 were analyzed by the cross-plot of peak amplitude vs. event duration. Typical number of signals analyzed were from several hundred to several thousand. It is found that the increase in signal energy with the degree of damage accounts not for higher peak amplitude but for longer event duration. Such a trend is more significant for type-A specimens than type-B specimens. This is due to the stacking sequence and the type-A specimens are more vulnerable to impact damage.

Figure 4 AE events vs. time during the monotonic tensile loading of (a) type-A specimen with 10% damage and (b) type-B specimen with 50% damage

Figure 5 Peak amplitude vs. event duration of AE signals from the analysis windows

Felicity Ratio vs. Integrity Ratio

Felicity ratio (FR) is defined as the ratio of the load at which significant emission restarts to the previously applied maximum load. From the series of loading-unloading-reloading experiments, FR values were obtained for both types of specimens with different degree of damage. For both type-A and type-B specimens, undamaged specimen and specimen damaged by 10% showed almost same values of FR. This implies that AE may not be an effective tool for detecting small amount of the impact damage up to 10%. This was also the case when ultrasonic C-scan was employed to examine the damage area with this specimen. In Fig. 6, FR values from each type of specimens are shown as the function of the degree of damage to compare with another ratio.

The newly proposed one named as integrity ratio has been defined as the ratio of the load at which a significant increase in rms voltage starts to the ultimate failure load. It was so named that the ratio rapidly decreases with the degree of damage as shown in Fig. 6. The ratio for type-A specimens decreases faster than those for type-B specimens. This is again due to the stacking sequence and the higher strength type-A specimens are more vulnerable to the progress or accumulation of damages. Although the definition of felicity ratio looks quite simple and clear, practically it is not very easy to determine the value during or even after experiments. The integrity ratio can be obtained after the experiment and may be applicable only for the damaged laminates as studied here but much easier to determine.

Figure 6 Felicity ratio with the fraction of ultimate load

Residual Strength

The standardized method for evaluating the residual strength of damaged composites is generally known as CAI (compression after impact) test [4]. AE activities were excellent parameters to quantify the degree of impact damage and the residual strength of composite laminates when they were tested under compression [5]. The compression test, however, consists of complicated fixtures and procedures and thus becomes an extremely expensive method [6].

Therefore, the tensile residual strength was tried to be correlated with the degree of impact damage in this study for its simplicity and cost-effectiveness of tensile tests. The result was disappointed with that there was no correlation between the degree of damage and the tensile residual strength. It was also unable to correlate the residual strength with AE activity from the impact-damaged composite laminates.

CONCLUSIONS

1. The analysis of AE signals from the initial tensile loading up to 50% of the ultimate strength can be utilized for the assessment of impact damages in composite laminates.
2. Both AE rms voltage and signal duration data appeared to be very useful parameters to evaluate the degree of damages.
3. A new parameter named as integrity ratio has been proposed as a useful index for the impact damage assessment of composite laminates, which appears to be more efficient than the traditional felicity ratio.
4. Although AE activity was clearly correlated with the degree of impact damage, it was unable to estimate the residual strength of composite laminates under tension by AE monitoring.

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